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A Comprehensive Review of the Concept of Psychological Climate and Suggestions for Creating a Positive Psychological Climate¹

Psikolojik İklim Kavramının Kapsamlı Bir İncelemesi ve Olumlu Psikolojik İklim Oluşturmaya Yönelik Öneriler

ABSTRACT

This study comprehensively addresses the concept of psychological climate. Psychological climate refers to all of an individual's positive and negative perceptions of the work environment. It is also one of the fundamental factors that guide an individual's behavior. Originating from Lewin's "field theory" the concept was developed in an organizational context through the work of Litwin and colleagues. Factors influencing psychological climate include trust and meaningfulness, supportive management, role clarity, self-expression, the perceived significance of organizational contribution, recognition, overcoming challenges, organizational experiences and leader-member interaction. Psychological climate directly affects factors such as job involvement, job satisfaction, organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behavior, empowerment and organizational performance. A positive psychological climate leads to significant improvements in these factors. It also enables employees to identify their personal goals with organizational goals, increasing their motivation and effort. Creating a positive psychological climate is crucial for organizational success. The conclusion of the study offers recommendations to managers on how to foster a positive psychological climate.

Keywords: Psychological Climate, Factors Influencing and Affected by Psychological Climate, Recommendations for Positive Psychological Climate.

ÖZET

Bu çalışma psikolojik iklim kavramını kapsamlı bir şekilde ele almaktadır. Psikolojik iklim, bireyin çalışma ortamına ilişkin olumlu olumsuz tüm algılarını ifade etmektedir. Psikolojik iklim aynı zamanda bireyin davranışlarına rehberlik eden temel faktörlerden biridir. Bu kavram Lewin'in "işyerindeki sosyal iklimler" teorisinden yola çıkılarak sonraki çalışmalarda örgütsel psikolojinin odak noktası olmuş ve geliştirilmiştir. Psikolojik iklimi etkileyen faktörler arasında güven ve anlamlılık, destekleyici yönetim, rol netliği, kendini ifade etme, örgütsel katkının anlamlılığı, tanınma, zorlukların üstesinden gelme, örgütsel deneyimler, lider üye etkileşimi gibi değişkenler yer almaktadır. Psikolojik iklim, iş benimseme, iş tatmini, örgütsel bağlılık, örgütsel vatandaşlık davranışı, güçlendirme, örgütsel performans gibi faktörler üzerinde doğrudan etkilidir. Olumlu psikolojik iklim bu faktörler üzerinde belirgin iyileştirmeler sağlar. Ayrıca çalışanların kişisel amaçlarını örgütsel amaçlarla özdeşleştirerek işlerinde daha fazla motive olmaları ve daha fazla çaba harcamalarına olanak tanır. Olumlu psikolojik iklimin oluşturulması örgütlerin başarısı için oldukça önemlidir. Son olarak çalışmanın sonuç kısmında olumlu psikolojik iklim oluşturulabilmesi için yöneticilere yönelik önerilere yer verilmiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Psikolojik İklim, Psikolojik İklimin Etkilendiği ve Etkilediği Faktörler, Olumlu Psikolojik İklim Önerileri.

¹ This article is derived from Yunus UÇAR's doctoral dissertation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Developments in information processing, communication and transportation technologies have brought about many changes and new management models in individual, social, and organizational contexts. With the transition from the information society to the surveillance society, organizations have abandoned rigid hierarchical and bureaucratic management approaches and adopted individual-oriented management models. Consequently, psychological climate has become a concept of interest and research in organizational psychology, as a result of organizations' shift toward individual-centered management models (Kaygısız, 2010: p.14).

Psychological climate can be conceptualized as a representation of an individual's cognitive perceptions of the work environment. This cognitive representation enables individuals to attribute meaning to organizational events and determine which behaviors are likely to produce the best outcomes (Parker et al., 2003: p.390-391). Psychological climate pertains to psychologically meaningful and measurable perceptions for the individual rather than concrete organizational characteristics (James et al., 1978: p.786-787). Changing individual perceptions is quite difficult. Therefore, attempts to change these perceptions must be made consistently and with considerable effort (Craig & Alan, 2006: p.420). Thus, in order to influence employees' perceptions of psychological climate, it is first necessary to understand the factors that affect it.

Each of the factors that influence psychological climate contributes to the perception of the work environment as psychologically safe and meaningful by individuals (Brown & Leigh, 1996: p.361). Trust indicates that employees feel close enough to their superiors to communicate openly on sensitive or personal issues and believe in them. Meaning, which can also be referred to as purpose, involves the alignment between job role requirements and the employee's beliefs, values, and behaviors (Craig & Alan, 2006: p.421). When individuals perceive the organizational environment as psychologically safe and meaningful, they identify their personal goals with those of the organization and exert greater effort to achieve them (Brown & Leigh, 1996: p.358). In other words, psychological climate is both a source of organizational strength and a fundamental value that unites all members of the organization in a cohesive force (Vuong et al., 2021: p.1021–1032). Therefore, each factor that helps employees perceive the organizational environment as safe and meaningful contributes to the development of a positive perception of psychological climate.

Psychological climate guides behavior by shaping an individual's work attitudes (James et al., 1978: p.786). As a result of work experiences and personal values, psychological climate significantly influences the emergence of emotional attachment to the organization (Biswas, 2009: p.22-32). Furthermore, because individuals have different needs, values, and learning experiences, psychological climate causes them to perceive friendship, job involvement, empowerment, job satisfaction, organizational citizenship and organizational justice differently (James & Sells, 1981: p.275). As a result, psychological climate influences an individual's work attitudes, performance outcomes and degree of job engagement (Clissold, 2006: p.1).

In this study, the literature on psychological climate is examined in detail, including the definition and historical development of the concept. The factors that influence and are influenced by psychological climate are identified. Determining the factors affected by psychological climate helps to better understand the importance of the concept, while identifying the influencing factors aims to provide recommendations for managers on how to create a positive psychological climate.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. The Concept of Psychological Climate

Individuals' perceptions of their work environment influence their attitudes and behaviors and these attitudes and behaviors, in turn affect their job performance. Both individual and environmental factors play a role in shaping these perceptions. Psychological climate is one of the environmental factors

composed of individuals' perceptions of the work environment and must be examined as a concept that affects productive work behavior (Güler, 2019: p.13).

The concept of climate, which is widely used in natural sciences has also become a central focus in the literature on management and organization, organizational psychology and human resource management. In management and organization literature, psychological climate refers to “a set of measurable features of the work environment that influence individuals' attitudes and behaviors” (Özek, 2018: p.101). In organizational psychology, it is defined as “individuals' perceptions of their work environment” (James et al., 1990: p.40).

Psychological climate is an individual perception of the internal organizational environment (Li et al., 2019: p.172-173). These individual perceptions can lead to genuine enjoyment of one's work or create psychological barriers. In this sense, psychological climate reflects a subjective condition of the current work environment that either facilitates heartfelt work engagement or imposes psychological constraints (Kahn,1990: p.694).

Psychological climate perceptions help individuals interpret events, predict possible outcomes and evaluate the appropriateness of their future actions (Jones & James, 1979: p.201). When individuals perceive the organizational environment positively, they engage more in their work and exert more effort. This leads to higher job performance. Conversely, when they perceive the environment negatively, they are less engaged and exert less effort, which leads to decreased performance (Muafi et al., 2020: p.593). In addition, psychological climate shapes attitudes and thus influences behaviors. In other words, it guides behavior in line with organizational goals and plays a crucial role in determining the quality of organizational life (James et al., 1978: p.786).

Values such as transparency, responsibility, supportiveness, and friendly social interactions serve as a model for individuals in assessing their work environment (Burke et al., 2002: p.325-340). Formed as a result of work experiences and individual values, psychological climate plays a critical role in the development of emotional commitment to the organization (Biswas, 2009: p.22-32). Therefore, psychological climate affects attitudes, performance outcomes and job engagement in relation to organizational policies, procedures and practices (Clissold, 2006: p.1).

According to Brown and Leigh (1996: p.358-368), psychological climate is “the general mood within an organization that emerges through individuals' psychological nuances.” It manifests through the relationship between top management and employees, relationships among employees, and employees' attitudes and behaviors toward their work. A positive psychological climate helps employees reach goals, brings joy and inspiration to their work, enhances communication among employees, boosts performance and fosters mutual respect. As a result, employees tend to prioritize collective interests over personal ones, perform their duties willingly, develop a sense of organizational commitment and voluntarily comply with organizational rules.

2.2. Theoretical Origins of the Concept of Psychological Climate

Climate research has a long history in industrial and organizational psychology and the concept of climate was first used in an industrial context by Lewin, Lippitt and White in the late 1930s. Beginning with Lewin et al., (1939: 271-299) use of the concept of “social climates” in the workplace, studies assessing climate perceptions have become increasingly interesting for researchers.

As it is currently examined, the concept of psychological climate was not extensively discussed until the late 1960s. Litwin and Stringer (1968: p.45-55) were the first to present a model concerning the determinants of motivated behavior within organizations, which included the concept of organizational climate. It should be noted that during the early stages of psychological climate research, it was often referred to as organizational climate. However, today the term “organizational climate” is used to describe shared perceptions of organizational policies and practices, rather than individual perceptions of workplace characteristics (Baltes, 2001: p.12355).

According to Litwin and Stringer (1968: p.49-50), climate is a concept related to employee satisfaction and performance. A climate that emphasizes individual responsibility is effective in stimulating the need for achievement. The “achievement climate” they describe characterized by high employee responsibility, strong cooperation among employees, tolerance for conflict and support for risk-taking leads to higher satisfaction and performance. Their research has served as a driving force for future studies on climate.

In the following period, James and Jones (1974: p.1096-1112) examined the climate literature and concluded that although climate research was quite interesting, the conceptual definition of climate, the measurement techniques used and the results obtained were quite diverse and contradictory. These inconsistencies made it difficult to fully understand the climate construct and contributed to its perception as a vague concept. To resolve this, James and Jones (1974: p.1096-1112) argued that researchers should distinguish between climate measured at the organizational level and psychological climate measured at the individual level. They asserted that psychological climate is a subjective, individual construct, where as organizational climate is an objective feature of the organization’s environment.

Schneider (1975: p.447-479), emphasizing the need to define and examine psychological and organizational climate as separate constructs, defined psychological climate as individual perceptions of organizational practices and procedures that are useful in understanding their effects on individual performance and satisfaction. Organizational climate, in contrast was defined as a collective description of the work environment, associated with organizational-level outcomes. According to Schneider (1975: p.447-479), clearly differentiating these definitions allows researchers to focus either on psychological or organizational climate, which in turn helps clarify their structure and their relationships with other variables, shaping future studies on the boundary between the two concepts.

James et al. (1978: p.784-785) explained the underlying assumptions and rationale of psychological climate through the lenses of cognitive social learning theory and interactionist psychology. From this perspective, they defined psychological climate as “cognitive representations of the situational conditions of the work environment, expressed in psychologically meaningful terms.” Their research suggested that psychological climate represents perceptual differences among individuals in the same situation and that these differences are psychologically significant. They argued that psychological climate should be regarded as a function of perception and cognitive information processing. Moreover, they emphasized that the subjective nature of perceptions related to objectively defined situations due to individual differences would continue to be of significant interest to researchers in terms of motivation, satisfaction and performance.

Kahn (1990: p.692-724) created the dimensions of psychological climate in his study in line with the findings regarding the psychological conditions that motivate employees to do their jobs better. The dimensions he developed reflect environmental factors that shape perceptions of “meaningfulness” and “safety.” According to Kahn (1990: p.692-724) the presence or absence of these climate factors affects whether employees are fully engaged or psychologically connected to their work. Generally, perceptions of psychological safety are influenced by dimensions such as supportive management, role clarity and self-expression, while perceptions of psychological meaningfulness are influenced by challenge, organizational contribution and recognition (Linsner, 2009: p.54).

Brown and Leigh (1996: p.358–362) operationalized psychological climate and conceptualized the notion of a “positive psychological climate.” A positive psychological climate helps employees not only find motivation and material rewards in their work but also perceive it as a source of spiritual fulfillment. It shows employees that they work in a safe and meaningful environment. According to Brown and Leigh (1996: p.360) define a “positive psychological climate” as an environment characterized by supportive management, opportunities for self-expression, clarity, perceived contribution, recognition and overcoming challenges. When these features are present, employees are more likely to focus on their work and become highly motivated (Linsner, 2009: 54-55).

2.3. Factors Affecting Psychological Climate

The factors affecting psychological climate arise from individual characteristics and situational conditions that lead individuals to perceive and interpret their work environment differently. These factors also considered dimensions of psychological climate include supportive management, role clarity, self-expression, perceived meaningfulness of contribution, organizational recognition, and overcoming challenges. These dimensions lead to differences in individual perceptions of the work environment. In this context, each dimension of psychological climate is considered one of the most important factors potentially influencing employees' attitudes and behaviors (Craig & Alan, 2006: p.420).

2.3.1. Supportive Management

The “supportive management” dimension of psychological climate reflects employees' perceptions of autonomy and control. This dimension includes employees' perceptions regarding whether their managers act flexibly in granting them control or autonomy over certain aspects of their jobs. Supportive management provides important implications for employees' perceptions of psychological safety. It reflects whether management expects strict discipline from employees or allows flexibility in task completion (Brown & Leigh, 1996: p.360).

Managers may adopt various approaches concerning organizational demands, monitoring subordinates' behavior, granting authority and empowering employees. A supportive management style allows subordinates to try new ideas and take risks without fear of punishment. It also allows them to control how they perform their tasks. Employees can explore new methods to achieve organizational goals and apply their creativity to problem solving. The autonomy, choice, and sense of security fostered by supportive management increase motivation and encourage greater task engagement. In contrast, a rigid or inflexible management style indicates a lack of trust in employees' ability to perform without close supervision (Kahn, 1990: p.692-724; Brown & Leigh, 1996: p.360).

Valas and Sovik (1993: p.283) note that managers or leaders who adopt a supportive and flexible style encourage employees to use their own methods while performing their tasks. Managers who consistently grant autonomy also help develop employees' sense of control. In addition to fostering autonomy, a psychologically supportive climate also enhances employees' sense of security (Kahn, 1990: p.692-724; Brown & Leigh, 1996: p.360).

The perception of autonomy is closely tied to the perception of psychological safety. Individuals feel more secure when their managers allow them some control over their work. Managers' reluctance to grant control over specific job tasks may send the message that employees are not trusted and should avoid stepping outside established boundaries (Kahn, 1990: p.692-724). Without a sense of security, it is difficult for employees to trust the autonomy granted to them. If managers continuously criticize employees after granting them autonomy, employees may perceive that making independent decisions is unsafe. In such cases, employees are more likely to perceive the psychological climate of the organization as unpredictable, rigid and unsafe (Linsner, 2009: p.66–67).

2.3.2. Role Clarity

Carless (2004: p.408) defines role clarity as “the degree to which job expectations and responsibilities are clearly defined.” Similarly, Csikszentmihalyi (1997: p.8-12) states that role clarity allows employees to perform organizational tasks without questioning what needs to be done or how they should behave. In other words, clarity means that employees know what is expected of them and feel psychologically safe when they behave accordingly. In such situations, employees can become fully motivated without constantly questioning every step they take in organizational activities.

When individuals constantly have to question their actions, their attention is diverted from the task, decreasing their motivation. Employees who are unsure about what constitutes acceptable behavior or what is expected of them in their roles tend to act more cautiously, which in turn reduces their motivation to engage in their duties (Linsner, 2009: p.64). Therefore, role clarity significantly influences an individual's sense of psychological safety and their perception of the psychological climate.

According to Brown and Leigh (1996: p.360) when role expectations and working conditions are ambiguous, inconsistent, or unpredictable, employees' perceptions of psychological safety weaken. As a result, task engagement and job commitment decrease. Kahn (1990: p.692-724) also emphasizes that ambiguity and inconsistency in role expectations undermine employees' trust in the autonomy granted to them. Conversely, clear expectations and consistent, predictable working norms create a psychologically safe work environment, which in turn enhances task engagement and job commitment.

2.3.3. Self-Expression

The “self-expression” dimension of psychological climate refers to employees' ability to freely express their thoughts and feelings within the organization. Employees who feel free to express themselves are more successful in making independent decisions and fulfilling their duties (O'Neill & Arendt, 2008: p.359).

When employees perceive that expressing their personal feelings and thoughts while performing their tasks may result in organizational sanctions, they psychologically detach from their roles and responsibilities. The freedom to express oneself is closely related to the perception of psychological safety. When individuals do not feel psychologically safe, they tend to fulfill their roles in a merely formal or mechanical way. On the other hand, when employees feel psychologically safe, they are more likely to align their personalities, creativity, emotions, and identities with their roles. This increases the likelihood that individuals will accept, internalize and personalize their roles and view them as an expression of their self (Brown & Leigh, 1996: p.360).

Ultimately, when employees feel safe in expressing their identities, emotions and thoughts, they are more likely to act in accordance with their roles and become more engaged in their work (Kahn, 1990: p.692-724; Schlenker, 1986: p.21-56). Therefore, Brown and Leigh (1996: p.360) state that the freedom of self-expression is positively related to job engagement. They suggest that self-expression significantly affects an individual's sense of psychological safety and consequently, their perception of psychological climate.

2.3.4. Perceived Meaningfulness of Contribution

Contribution refers to the perception that an individual's work has an impact on organizational performance and outcomes and that it makes a difference for the organization. The perception of contribution influences the meaning individuals derive from their work and consequently, their psychological climate perceptions. When individuals believe that they are making a meaningful contribution to the organization, they feel valued and useful; they believe they are making a difference and that their efforts are taken seriously. A lack of perceived meaningful contribution is associated with the belief that little is expected of them at work and that there is little they can contribute to the organization's goals (Kahn, 1990: p.704).

Brown and Leigh (1996: p.360) used the term “contribution” to describe a climate where individuals feel useful and appreciated. According to them, the perception that one's work significantly affects organizational processes and outcomes contributes to the perceived meaningfulness of the task and fosters identification with one's work role. Moreover, when individuals believe they are contributing meaningfully to organizational goals, they are more engaged in their work.

Kahn (1990: p.692-724) emphasizes that the feeling of making a contribution is meaningful and important, as having a sense of purpose meets individuals' psychological needs. He argues that when individuals perceive the organization as meeting their psychological needs, they devote more time and energy to their work. Therefore, the feeling of contribution enhances the perceived meaningfulness of work, which in turn positively influences motivation, task internalization and job engagement. Conversely, when individuals believe their efforts are insignificant or unappreciated, they are less motivated and experience lower satisfaction with their work.

2.3.5. Organizational Recognition

Employees' perceptions that their efforts are acknowledged and appreciated are referred to as “recognition” (Brown & Leigh, 1996: p.360). Carless (2004: p.408) defines recognition as “the extent to

which employees receive feedback regarding acceptance and approval.” Recognition increases the perceived meaningfulness of the work. When individuals believe their work is important and valued, they develop a strong sense of duty. Recognition also implies that the work being done is approved, which leads employees to believe that their future efforts will also be appreciated and seen as meaningful (Brown & Leigh, 1996: p.360).

Research shows that recognition is a significant factor in motivating employees to exert greater effort. When employees believe that the organization appreciates and acknowledges their efforts and contributions, the perceived meaningfulness of their work increases. Employees who feel their contributions are beneficial and recognized are more likely to identify with their roles and tasks and become more engaged in their duties (Kahn, 1990: p.692-724; Brown & Leigh, 1996: p.360).

Brown and Leigh (1996: p.360) state that recognition is directly related to employee effort and contributes to a positive psychological climate that encourages job engagement. Recognition serves as a type of feedback that fosters a positive perception of the psychological climate and due to the meaning it conveys, motivates employees to exert greater effort (Hackman & Oldham, 1975: p.161-162; Bakker, 2005: p.27-28). When recognition is perceived as meaningful in its various forms, employees are more likely to increase their effort and focus on their work. Conversely, when employees feel that their efforts go unnoticed and unrecognized, they feel unappreciated, develop negative perceptions of the psychological climate and become less motivated to put in effort (Brown & Leigh, 1996: p.360).

2.3.6. Overcoming Challenges

The dimension of overcoming challenges refers to the idea that a job is demanding and requires high levels of skill and ability to be performed effectively (Brown & Leigh, 1996: p.361). In other words, the perception that a task requires taking risks, being open to change and using creativity in order to be completed successfully is described as overcoming professional challenges (Koys & DeCotiis, 1991: p.273).

Generally, individuals are more motivated when they perceive a match between the inherent difficulty of a task and their ability to cope with it (Clarke & Haworth, 1994: p.511-523). Managers have a certain degree of control over the alignment between the level of professional challenge and employees’ abilities to overcome them. While job descriptions play a critical role in defining the difficulty level of a task, managers can do much to ensure a good fit between employees’ skill levels and the opportunities available to apply those skills. In other words, rather than assigning employees to tasks that underutilize their abilities, they should be given roles that allow them to fully use their skills and provide opportunities for development (Bakker, 2005: p.27-28; Linsner, 2009: p.62).

Personal development within a job typically occurs when the job is challenging and requires the use of diverse skills and creativity. Challenging jobs encourage employees to invest more physical, cognitive and emotional energy into their work and enhance the perceived meaningfulness of the task (Kahn, 1990: p.692-724). When the perceived meaningfulness of the task increases, so does employee motivation and the effort they put into their jobs. This directly influences their perception of the psychological climate.

2.3.7. Organizational Experiences

Both psychological climate and behavior are constructs that operate at the individual level. Social learning theory suggests that perceptions of psychological climate reflect employees’ general thoughts and interpretations of their organizational experiences and that these perceptions remain relatively stable over time (Rousseau, 1985: p.1-2). Before taking action, employees need to perceive and interpret their work environments (James et al., 2008: p.5). Perception is the process by which an individual interprets an event by considering their past experiences and psychological needs (Özek, 2014: p.154).

In the field of organizational behavior, climate is considered one of the key environmental factors influencing employees’ attitudes and behaviors. Therefore, an individual’s past experiences and accumulated knowledge influence their perception of psychological climate and in turn, psychological climate influences the individual’s attitudes and behaviors (Schneider et al., 2013: p.361).

2.3.8. Leader-Member Exchange (LMX)

Research on leader-member exchange (LMX) has revealed that managers treat different subordinates differently based on their varying competencies (Xanthopoulou et al., 2008: p.345-356). Competence, also referred to as self-efficacy, reflects the degree to which an employee believes they possess the skills and abilities necessary to successfully complete a given task (Craig & Alan, 2006: p.421). Since individuals differ in terms of their levels of competence, their perceptions of the same work environment vary depending on differences in individual capabilities and the quality of their interpersonal relationships with their supervisors (Dansereau et al., 1975: p.46-78; Dienesch & Liden, 1986: p.618-634; Xanthopoulou et al., 2008: p.345-356).

According to Woerkom and Meyers (2015: p.83-84) employees form different interpretations of organizational practices and workplace conditions based on their personal interactions with their supervisors. As a result, individual perceptions of the work environment vary depending on leader-member relationships. Linsner (2009: p.102-125) in a study examining the effect of transformational leadership on psychological climate and its dimensions, found that transformational leadership was significantly associated with all dimensions of psychological climate and had a positive influence on it.

2.3.9. Personality Traits

In their study on the relationship between personality traits and performance, Tett and Burnett (2003: p.500-517) argued that various situational cues at different organizational levels influence employees' personality traits, thereby shaping their behaviors. In workplace settings, personality-related cues can be grouped into three categories: task-level expectations, social-level expectations and organizational-level expectations. As a result of their personality traits, individuals may display varying degrees of motivation in the workplace. Therefore, depending on their personalities, individuals may perceive the same situation differently, which in turn affects their job motivation and performance.

2.3.10. Other Factors

Differences in psychological climate can also arise from variations in management styles within the same organization or from differing organizational cultures across institutions (Brown & Leigh, 1996: p.359). In a study examining the influence of organizational culture and psychological climate on perceptions of political behavior, Mohammed (2011: p.111-112) found that organizational culture significantly affects perceptions of psychological climate.

Role-related characteristics such as workload and job clarity are among the factors influencing psychological climate. Workload refers to the quantity of tasks as well as the degree to which employees have the necessary resources (time, equipment, support) to complete them. Job clarity refers to the extent to which job requirements and task definitions are predefined. While excessive workload negatively affects psychological climate, job clarity has a positive influence (Özek, 2014: p.157).

Job characteristics such as task significance and autonomy are also key factors that influence psychological climate. When employees perceive their job as important, they tend to view it as meaningful and the satisfaction derived from job success increases (Özek, 2014: p.157). Autonomy refers to the degree to which employees can determine their own work procedures (Craig & Alan, 2006: p.420). Autonomy encourages employees to take initiative and responsibility. Thus, job characteristics significantly influence employees' perceptions of psychological climate.

Organizational features such as perceived support and justice also shape employees' psychological climate perceptions. Perceived support reflects employees' views that their superiors are encouraging and tolerant, while perceived justice refers to the belief that supervisory decisions are fair and impartial (Craig & Alan, 2006: p.420). Finally, physical conditions of the work environment such as lighting, noise and temperature

as well as demographic variables like age, gender, income, education and position also affect individual perceptions and interpretations, thereby influencing psychological climate (Özek, 2014: p.157-161).

2.4. Factors Affected by Psychological Climate

Psychological climate influences an individual's thoughts, feelings and behaviors. While the previous section of the study identified the dimensions and factors that shape employees' perceptions of the psychological climate, this section discusses how psychological climate affects work-related outcomes. Understanding these outcomes more clearly demonstrates the importance of the concept of psychological climate. Numerous studies in the literature have shown that psychological climate has a significant impact on work attitudes and performance outcomes such as job involvement, job satisfaction, organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behavior, psychological empowerment and organizational performance.

2.4.1. The Impact of Psychological Climate on Job Involvement

Lodahl and Kejner (1965: p.24) define job involvement as "the degree of an individual's psychological identification with their job or the importance of the job in their cognition." Job involvement is a more valid concept for individuals for whom work constitutes the most important part of their lives. Job involvement is a phenomenon that emerges from the interactions between an individual's personality traits and their varying sensitivities to work environments (Ruh et al., 1975: p.300-312).

Job engagement is directly influenced by an individual's perceptions of the work environment and their close relationships (Ruh et al., 1975: p.300-312). Other factors affecting job engagement include job characteristics such as autonomy, skill variety, task identity and task significance; supervisory behaviors such as evaluation and participation and individual differences such as work motivation and work ethics (Brockner et al., 1988: p.436-442; Biswas, 2009: p.25; Lodahl & Kejner, 1965: p.24).

Some studies have shown that job engagement, influenced by the perception of psychological climate, is related to effort (Efraty & Sirgy, 1990: p.31). Time and energy are the two most fundamental resources employees can allocate to their organizations. These resources, used to operationalize effort, are ultimately entirely under employees' control. Given this high degree of voluntary control, it can be concluded that effort is influenced by employees' perceptions of psychological climate. When employees perceive the organization as meeting their psychological needs, they respond by investing more time and energy in their tasks. This leads to a direct and positive relationship between psychological climate and employee effort (Kahn, 1990: p.692-724).

The results of a study by Brown and Leigh (1996: p.358) indicate that psychological climate perception is related to job engagement and job engagement is related to effort. According to Brown and Leigh (1996: p.358) effort is also related to job performance. When employees perceive the work environment as positive, they identify their personal goals with the organization's goals and expend more effort to achieve them. According to Kahn (1990: p.692-724), the more individuals psychologically identify with their jobs, the more time and energy they devote to work-related activities.

2.4.2. The Impact of Psychological Climate on Empowerment

Empowerment is a general term that reflects a wide range of managerial styles and concerns encompassing a wide range of practices in human resources management (Lashley, 1996: p.336-337). According to Ford and Fottler (1995: p.21-22), "empowerment is commonplace" and generally refers to granting employees the autonomy to decide how to conduct their daily activities. The concept of empowerment, derived from participative management theories, supports the idea that managers should share decision-making processes and power with subordinates to improve organizational performance (Craig & Alan, 2006: p.419-420).

Two distinct but related theories of empowerment have been identified in the literature (Hardy & Leiba-O'Sullivan, 1998: p.451-483). These are the relational approach to empowerment and the motivational or

psychological approach. The relational approach is characterized by practices that decentralize power by involving employees in the decision-making process. The motivational approach suggests that empowerment is the result of experienced psychological states or perceptions (Thomas & Velthouse, 1990: p.666-681). The focus of this approach is on employees' perceptions of their individual power to cope with the events, situations and people they encounter in the workplace (Stewart & Manz, 1997: p.169-196). The motivational approach places less emphasis on delegation and instead advocates open communication, inspiring goal setting, incentives and feedback to increase commitment and participation (Conger & Kanungo, 1988: p.472-473). Although the motivational approach is broader in scope, it is an outgrowth of the relational approach. Therefore, it is accepted that the two approaches are different but also have similarities (Spreitzer, 1995: p.1443-1444).

Empowerment is a concept influenced by managers' behaviors and practices as a psychological consequence of subordinates' perceptions of four dimensions: meaningfulness, competence, autonomy and impact (Hancer & George, 2003: p.3-16; Lee & Koh, 2001: p.684-695). This definition, which emphasizes both the relational (the relationship between manager and subordinate) and motivational aspects of empowerment, expresses the idea that empowerment cannot occur among equals and its inclusive nature is accepted because it reveals the connection between some antecedents and outcomes of the structure (Amenume & Lockwood, 2008: p.269-270). Meaningfulness involves the congruence between the requirements of a work role and an individual's beliefs, values and behaviors (Spreitzer, 1995: p.1443-1444). Competence is an individual's belief in their capacity to adequately perform a work-related task. Autonomy, on the other hand, refers to the degree to which employees can determine their own work procedures (Craig & Alan, 2006: p.420). Influence is the degree to which an individual can change strategic, administrative or operational outcomes in the workplace. In other words, it is the extent of personal control over organizational outcomes or the individual's belief that they can make a difference in the workplace (Carless, 2004: p.407).

Research in the field of organizational behavior supports the proposition that perceptions of psychological climate influence employees' perceived empowerment. According to Spreitzer (1996: s.483-484) employees in a participatory psychological climate that values individual contribution and employee initiative perceive greater meaning, competence, autonomy and impact in their work (Craig & Alan, 2006: p.421).

Empowerment theories emphasize the importance of the organizational environment or context and suggest that empowerment is directly influenced by the work environment (Conger & Kanungo, 1988: p.472-473; Spreitzer, 1996: p.483-484; Thomas & Velthouse, 1990: p.666-681). These theories state that psychological climate is the primary factor shaping perceptions of empowerment (Carless, 2004: p.408-409). The relationship between psychological climate and empowerment is based on Hackman and Oldham's (1980: p.124-125) job characteristics theory and Thomas and Velthouse's (1990: p.666-681) empowerment model. Even if job and environmental characteristics are the same for two individuals, interpretations and evaluations of these characteristics vary due to differences in individual perceptions (James & McIntyre, 1996: p.420). Therefore, based on the theories explained above, it is stated that employees' evaluations of the work environment influence their perceptions of empowerment (Carless, 2004: p.408-409).

There are very few studies in the literature examining the relationship between psychological climate and empowerment. Amenumey and Lockwood (2008: p.265-281) examined the relationship between psychological climate and psychological empowerment. Their findings indicate a positive relationship between psychological climate and psychological empowerment.

Craig and Alan (2006: p.421-422) stated in their study that employees' perceptions of psychological climate are critical in shaping their perceptions of psychological empowerment. According to Craig and Alan (2006: p.421-422) psychological climate positively affects employees' perceived psychological empowerment when support, justice, trust, commitment, autonomy, innovation and recognition increase, while pressure decreases.

Previous research on psychological climate has revealed that the primary function of psychological climate is to guide and shape employees' behavior, ensuring that it aligns with organizational expectations (Koys & DeCotiis, 1991: p.265-285). Pressure, a dimension of psychological climate, is generally perceived as a negative influence on employees. When employees are constantly pressured to achieve goals and meet standards, they experience less satisfaction with their jobs and feel underappreciated within their organizations. As this perceived pressure increases, employees' personal decision-making power is likely to weaken and thus their sense of organizational commitment decreases (Swift & Campbell, 1998: p.27-37). Carless (2004: p.405-425) examined the hypothesis that empowerment mediates the relationship between psychological climate and job satisfaction. The results indicate that employees' perceptions of their work environment directly influence their perceptions of empowerment. This study demonstrates that employees' perceptions of key aspects of the work's psychological climate, such as leadership style, interpersonal relationships, professional development opportunities and individual-organizational goal congruence have a strong influence on their perceptions of empowerment and individual abilities.

2.4.3. The Impact of Psychological Climate on Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a psychological phenomenon that reflects an individual's feelings about their job (Carless, 2004: s.409-410). Job satisfaction refers to the extent to which an individual's expectations, shaped by their needs, desires and experiences are met or matched by the rewards received (Davis & Nestrom, 1985: p.109). Job satisfaction also means performing a job they enjoy and being rewarded for their efforts (Kaliski, 2007: p.446).

Employees' job satisfaction levels can range from extreme satisfaction to extreme dissatisfaction. In addition to holding attitudes toward their jobs as a whole, individuals also hold attitudes toward various aspects of their jobs, such as the type of work they perform, their coworkers, their superiors, their subordinates, their salaries and their promotion opportunities (George & Jones, 2008: p.78). In this respect, job satisfaction refers to a subjective evaluation of an individual's job as a whole or specific aspects of it (Macias & DeBustillo, 2014: p.3451). Therefore, the characteristics of the job and psychological states influence job satisfaction (Hackman & Oldham, 1980: p.126-127).

Job satisfaction is also defined as the degree of accomplishment an individual experiences regarding their job. Therefore, job satisfaction expresses the enthusiasm and happiness an individual feels for their job. It is generally directly related to psychological well-being as well as individual productivity. Job satisfaction is one of the fundamental factors that enables an individual to achieve satisfaction with job-related aspects such as recognition, income and promotion, and facilitates the achievement of organizational goals (Kaliski, 2007: p.446).

Job satisfaction is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon that has different meanings for different individuals. Job satisfaction is linked to motivation but it is not the same thing. Job satisfaction refers to an individual's attitude toward their job and is often associated with a sense of accomplishment, either quantitative or qualitative (Mullins, 2005: p.700). Therefore, job satisfaction is a key factor that motivates employees and encourages them to achieve better results (Raziq & Maulabakhsh, 2015: p.717-725).

Job satisfaction is one of the fundamental factors affecting organizational productivity. A high level of job satisfaction indicates a good emotional and mental state for individuals. Individuals' job satisfaction levels influence their behavior, which in turn influences the organization's functioning and operations. Therefore, it can be concluded that job satisfaction leads to positive behaviors, while job dissatisfaction leads to negative behaviors (Aziri, 2011: p.78-79).

An analysis of job satisfaction reveals the logic that a satisfied employee is a happy employee and a happy employee is a successful employee. The importance of job satisfaction becomes evident when considering that job dissatisfaction leads to many negative outcomes, such as lack of loyalty, increased absenteeism, increased workplace accidents, and intention to leave (Dziuba et al., 2020: p.18-25).

As previously mentioned, psychological climate concerns how employees' perceptions of the work environment affect their motivation, work attitudes and behaviors. Numerous empirical and meta-analytical studies support the impact of psychological climate perceptions on job outcomes such as job

satisfaction and performance (Baltes et al., 2003: p.3-17; Parker et al., 2003: p.389-416; Carr et al., 2003: p.605-619; Brown & Leigh, 1996: p.358-368; Abramis, 1994: p.1411-1433; Evans & Dion, 1991: p.175-186).

Parker et al. (2003: p.389-416) examined the relationship between psychological climate and individual job outcomes, taking into account the five dimensions of psychological climate developed by Jones and James (1979: p.201-250) (job, role ambiguity and conflict, leader, work group, and organization). The results of this study supported the relationship between psychological climate perceptions and job satisfaction, job attitudes, motivation, psychological well-being and performance. They also found that psychological climate perceptions had stronger relationships with job satisfaction, attitudes, psychological well-being than with motivation and performance.

The job dimension of psychological climate consists of three sub-level variables: job importance, job difficulty and job autonomy. Job importance is the degree to which the job is perceived to make a meaningful contribution and is important to the organization. Job difficulty is defined as the degree to which the job provides the perceived opportunity to determine the nature of tasks or problems. Job autonomy is defined as the perceived opportunity for an employee to act without consultation or permission and to fully utilize their abilities, skills and knowledge (James & Sells, 1981: p.282). Studies have generally found that job importance, job difficulty and job autonomy are determinants of job satisfaction across various work environments and cultures (Carvajal & Hardigan, 2000: p.420-425; DeCarlo & Agarwal, 1999: p.51-62; Dart, 1988: p.22-35; Swift & Campbell, 1998: p.27-37; Alpass et al., 1997: p.227-249).

The leader dimension of psychological climate consists of trust in the leader, the leader's setting of strong goals, the leader's facilitation and the leader's support. Trust in the leader is the perceived degree of trust in the leader. Leader goal empowerment refers to the degree to which the leader is perceived as encouraging subordinate participation in achieving group goals. Leader facilitation refers to the degree to which the leader is perceived as participating, guiding and providing solutions to problems in achieving group goals. Leader support refers to the degree to which the leader is perceived as aware of subordinate needs is perceived as sensitive to them and acts thoughtfully (James & Sells, 1981: p.282). All of these factors have been found to have a consistently and significantly impact on employee job satisfaction in work environments (Boselie & Van der Wiele, 2002: p.165-172; Mullen et al., 1989: p.155-169; Alpass et al., 1997: p.227-249).

Workgroup intimacy, pride in the workgroup, and cooperation within the workgroup are factors that constitute the workgroup dimension of the psychological climate. Workgroup intimacy refers to the degree of perceived friendly relations, trust and mutual affection among workgroup members. Workgroup pride is the degree to which an individual perceives satisfaction with their coworkers and the group's success. Workgroup cooperation is the perceived degree of collaborative effort among workgroup members to accomplish tasks (James & Sells, 1981, p. 283). Parker et al. (2003, p. 389-416) concluded in their study that factors related to the workgroup dimension of psychological climate are significantly related to job satisfaction and employees' job attitudes. Similarly, Boles and Babin (1996, p. 41-51) and Boselie and Van der Wiele (2002, p. 165-172) also reported that group cooperation is strongly and positively related to job satisfaction.

2.4.4. The Impact of Psychological Climate on Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Organizational citizenship behavior refers to the extent to which individuals comply with the behaviors the organization expects them to exhibit and beyond (Eisele & D'Amato, 2011: p.9). When individuals identify with and feel connected to their group, they are more likely to accept the norms and values of that group and are more likely to comply with its rules (Salancik & Pfeffer, 1977: p.427-456). Furthermore, the more individuals embrace the organization's goals and rules and believe they are appropriate for themselves, the more they will comply with the rules and procedures. This means that individuals will choose behaviors that align with the organization's goals (Koys, 2001: p.101-114; Organ, 1988: p.4).

Organizational citizenship behavior is a multidimensional concept that encompasses all positive organizational behaviors of organizational members, including traditional in-role behaviors, organizationally appropriate extra-role behaviors and political behaviors such as full and responsible organizational participation (Van Dyne et al., 1994: p.765-802). Organizational citizenship behavior is defined as “work behaviors that are not explicitly recognized by the formal reward system, are discretionary, contribute to the effectiveness of the organization and are performed voluntarily” (Organ, 1988: p.4). Similarly, organizational citizenship behavior is also defined as “extra-role behavior that is voluntary, goes beyond current role expectations and is intended to benefit the organization” (Van Dyne et al., 1995: p.218).

Employees’ willingness to exert effort beyond the formal obligations required by their positions is considered a fundamental component of effective organizational performance. The effective achievement of organizational goals depends on the effective performance of organizational functions. Therefore, for organizational functions to be effective and the continuity of the organization to be maintained, individuals must be willing to contribute to collaborative efforts within the organization and expend extra effort (Jahangir et al., 2004: p.77).

McClelland (1961: 3p.6-63) argued that organizational citizenship behavior can be better understood when viewed as motivation-based behaviors. According to McClelland (1961: p.36-63) all individuals possess some degree of achievement, affiliation and power motivation. Achievement motivation drives people to perform to a standard of excellence by desiring the accomplishment of a task, challenge or competition. Affiliation motivation drives people to establish and maintain relationships with others. The power motive, on the other hand, pushes people toward statuses and situations where they can control the work or actions of others.

Smith et al. (1983: p.653-663) define organizational citizenship behavior as a behavior with two fundamental dimensions: “altruism and generalized compliance.” Altruism is a helping behavior directed at specific individuals. When individuals experience specific problems and need assistance, altruistic people go the extra mile to help them. The other dimension of organizational citizenship behavior, generalized compliance, relates to an individual’s conscientiousness and refers to doing things “right and appropriately” for their own well-being not for a specific person.

Numerous studies in the literature explore the relationship between psychological climate and organizational citizenship behavior. Thayer (2008: p.69-73) examined the relationship between psychological climate, employee commitment and organizational citizenship behavior. The findings of the study revealed that psychological climate is positively related to both organizational citizenship behavior and employee commitment.

Biswas (2010: p.411-423) examined the mediating role of affective commitment between psychological climate and organizational citizenship behavior in a study using data from manufacturing and service businesses in India. The results of the study revealed a positive and significant relationship between psychological climate and organizational citizenship behavior, with affective commitment playing a mediating role in this relationship.

Eisele and D'Amato (2011: p.4-21) also investigated the mediating role of organizational citizenship behavior in the relationship between psychological climate and performance. In their study of 599 nurses and other healthcare workers in a Swedish hospital, they concluded that there was a strong positive relationship between psychological climate and organizational citizenship behavior.

Suratman et al. (2021: p.1019-1029) tested the effects of psychological climate, self-resilience, organizational citizenship behavior and job stress on employee performance during the COVID-19 pandemic on 316 participants working in various organizations in Indonesia. One of the findings of the study is that psychological climate has a significant and positive impact on organizational citizenship behavior and performance. Therefore, when examining the relationship between psychological climate and organizational citizenship, it can be concluded that a positive perception of psychological climate positively affects organizational citizenship behavior.

2.4.5. The Impact of Psychological Climate on Job Performance

Job performance refers to the results of all activities of employees, such as the products they produce or the outputs they achieve in the workplace. Job performance is divided into three categories: task performance, contextual performance and innovative performance (Bayrakçı et al., 2022: p.46). Task performance is the fulfillment of job descriptions assigned to employees (Satavuthi & Chaipoopirutana, 2014: p.65-66). Borman (2014: p.238-241) defines contextual performance as employees' willingness to undertake tasks not included in their job descriptions, their best efforts to succeed in their jobs, their willingness to work collaboratively and their compliance with workplace rules. Innovative performance, on the other hand, is the individual's continuous openness to innovation and their self-improvement, both individually and organizationally (Crescenzia & Gagliardi, 2018: p.482-483). Individuals' positive perceptions of their environment are reflected in their job performance. Since a positive psychological climate in the organizations in which employees work is reflected in their activities, their job performance also increases. As many studies have shown, there is a positive relationship between job performance and psychological climate (Bayrakçı et al., 2022: p.46-47).

Bayrakçı et al. (2022: p.52-53) examined the relationship between psychological climate and job performance in their study of 397 teachers working in Kocaeli during the 2020-2021 academic year. The study concluded that teachers had positive perceptions of the support, contribution and role clarity provided by the school administration but they experienced uncertainty about expressing themselves. Furthermore, teachers generally perceived the psychological climate in schools as positive and found their performance to be adequate. The study also indicated that a positive psychological climate perception contributed to increased job performance of teachers. Suratman et al. (2021: p.1019-1029) investigated the impact of psychological climate, self-resilience, organizational citizenship behavior and job stress on employee performance by conducting a survey on 316 employees of various Indonesian businesses who worked from home for a minimum of two months during the COVID-19 period. The study concluded that psychological climate and self-resilience had a significant and positive impact on organizational citizenship behavior and performance.

Bowen and Ostroff (2004: p.203-221) investigated whether a strong organizational climate mediates the relationship between the human resources management system and organizational performance. They concluded that psychological climates foster the development of organizational climate because strong human resources management systems reduce variability in employees' individual perceptions and behaviors. A stronger organizational climate contributes to performance by fostering behaviors consistent with the organization's goals.

Parker et al. (2003: p.395) examined whether job attitudes (job satisfaction, job involvement and job commitment), psychological well-being and motivation are influenced by psychological climate and whether these mediate the impact of psychological climate on organizational outcomes such as performance. The study's results supported the view that there is a significant relationship between psychological climate and job attitudes, motivation, psychological well-being and employee performance. Furthermore, the study found that job attitudes and motivation fully mediate the effect of psychological climate on employee performance.

Brown and Leigh (1996: p.358-368) examined the relationship between psychological climate and job involvement, effort and performance. They concluded that two specific dimensions of psychological climate, security and meaningfulness have a direct impact on job involvement and effort. The results revealed that positive psychological climate is more strongly related to job involvement, supporting the study's hypothesis that, in this case, positive psychological climate is associated with higher performance due to the mediating role of effort. Therefore, when studies examining the relationship between psychological climate and job performance are taken into consideration, it can be concluded that strong and positive psychological climates positively affect the job performance of the individual.

2.4.6. The Impact of Psychological Climate on Organizational Commitment

Organizational commitment refers to the strong emotional bond established between employees and their organization (Zencirkiran & Keser, 2018: p.275). Organizational commitment is defined as “a psychological state that characterizes employees’ relationship with the organization and influences their decision to maintain or terminate membership in the organization” (Woznyj et al., 2019: p.122-123; Suharto et al., 2020: p.1200-1203).

Organizational commitment has three dimensions: affective commitment, continuance commitment and normative commitment. Affective commitment refers to an employee’s emotional attachment to organizational values or the extent to which the employee likes the organization. Affective commitment is largely related to employee satisfaction (Wang & Zhang, 2022: p.497-524). A high level of emotional commitment felt by employees toward their organization leads to positive outcomes, such as intense effort spent on behalf of the organization (Zencirkiran & Keser, 2018: p.275). Continuance commitment relates to the extent to which employees feel the need to remain with their organization. The possible reasons for this desire vary. However, the main reasons are a lack of job alternatives and lower wages. On the other hand, individuals who have been with the organization for a longer period of time form a stronger bond than those who have been with the organization for a shorter period of time (Wang & Zhang, 2020: p.497-524). Normative commitment, on the other hand, means that employees do not consider leaving their job due to a sense of indebtedness and commitment to the opportunities provided by the organization (Zencirkiran & Keser, 2018: p.277). Employees with normative commitment generally believe they should continue working at their organization. Normatively committed employees believe that leaving the organization will have disastrous consequences for them and feel guilty about leaving (Wang & Zhang, 2020: p.497-524).

Of the three types of commitment, individuals voluntarily choose to remain with the organization only when they feel emotional commitment. Continuance and normative commitment involve staying with the organization not out of their own volition but for a variety of reasons. Therefore, it can be said that the type of commitment that favors organizations is emotional commitment (Zencirkiran & Keser, 2018: p.277). Qing et al. (2019: p.1405-1432) state that emotional commitment consists of three components: (a) absolute belief in the organization's values and goals, (b) making every effort necessary for the organization's benefit and (c) a strong desire to remain with the organization.

Kawiana et al. (2020: p.1058) investigated the impact of leadership and psychological climate on organizational commitment in a study conducted on 216 managers and employees in different businesses in Bali, Indonesia. The results of the study revealed that all dimensions of psychological climate have a significant and positive relationship with employees’ organizational commitment. According to Kawiana et al. (2020: p.1058), psychological climate has a significant and positive effect on organizational commitment, indicating that a supportive psychological climate increases employees’ commitment to the organization.

Parker et al. (2003: p.389-416) stated in their study that positive psychological climate is one of the important factors influencing employee behavior. They also stated that psychological climate and employee commitment are important factors in organizational success. Similarly, James et al. (1990: p.40-84) concluded that dimensions of psychological climate, such as trust, autonomy, commitment, pressure, support, recognition, justice and innovation have a significant impact in explaining organizational commitment.

Langkamer and Ervin (2008: p.219-236) hypothesized that psychological climate and affective commitment have direct and indirect effects on intention to leave the military and examined how work experiences influence military personnel’s intention to leave the military. Data were collected through surveys administered to 649 military personnel. They concluded that psychological climate influences the emotional commitment and morale of military personnel, which in turn influences their intention to leave the military. Furthermore, they found that psychological climate, affective commitment and morale have the greatest impact on intention to leave the military, and that affective commitment and morale play a mediating role in the effect of psychological climate on intention to leave the military. Biswas (2009: p.22-32) tested the mediating role of affective commitment between psychological climate and job commitment in his study using data collected from 357 participants working in manufacturing and service sectors across

India. The results confirmed the hypothesis that affective commitment plays a mediating role in the relationship between psychological climate and job commitment. Furthermore, the results suggest that a positive psychological climate is associated with an individual's psychological empowerment.

This in turn has been shown to lead to a positive attitude change toward the conduct of work. This explains the role of the psychological climate in positively influencing employees' affective, normative and continuance commitment to their organizations. Therefore, a positive psychological climate enables individuals to expand their scope of activity and increase their commitment to their organizations.

3. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Increasing global competition today has made it necessary for organizations to use all their resources more effectively and efficiently. Activities aimed at the effective and efficient use of human resources have gained even greater importance today (Uçar & Özdemir, 2025: p.290). In recent years, organizations have abandoned rigid hierarchical and bureaucratic management approaches and embraced individual-focused management models. As a result of this, the concept of psychological climate has been continuously developed throughout the historical process stretching from the work of Lewin et al. (1939) to the present day, becoming an indispensable element for organizational success and the focus of numerous studies in organizational psychology.

In this study, the relationships between the concept of psychological climate and intra-organizational behavioral dynamics were analyzed to understand the individual-focused transformation of organizational life; the impact of psychological climate on employee attitudes and behaviors was discussed in a multidimensional manner. Various empirical studies have demonstrated that the components that influence psychological climate such as trust, meaningfulness, perception of support and justice, autonomy, contribution, recognition, overcoming challenges, leadership style, personality traits, organizational culture, role and job characteristics and the physical characteristics of the work environment have impacted job satisfaction, job commitment, organizational citizenship behavior and performance.

Psychological climate is one of the fundamental factors that makes an organization successful. Employees' perceptions and experiences of the work environment directly affect not only their personal well-being but also the organization's performance, productivity and competitiveness. Therefore, it is crucial for managers to focus on creating and maintaining a positive psychological climate.

A positive psychological climate helps employees perceive that participation in their duties is valuable in terms of achieving tangible and intangible benefits. Furthermore, a positive psychological climate perception gives employees the feeling of having a meaningful and safe work environment. When these climate characteristics are present, employees are more motivated and exert more effort in their work (Linsner, 2009: p.54-55).

This study is expected to contribute to the literature by examining the concept of psychological climate in a multidimensional and detailed manner. Furthermore, some suggestions are made for business managers to create a positive psychological climate:

The control, freedom of choice, and sense of security created by a supportive management style increase motivation and encourage greater engagement (Kahn, 1990: p.692-724; Brown and Leigh, 1996: p.360). By providing employees with control and autonomy over certain aspects of their work, managers can both increase their motivation and positively influence their perceptions of trust, thereby creating a positive psychological climate.

Kahn (1990: p.692-724) states that clear expectations appropriate to employees' roles, consistent and predictable work norms, create a psychologically safe work environment, which in turn increases engagement and commitment to the job. In this context, when job and task descriptions are clearly defined and expectations of employees are clearly defined, employees' perceptions of trust, commitment to the job, and engagement can be increased and a positive psychological climate can be fostered. When employees can freely express their feelings and thoughts, they feel more psychologically secure. In this case, employees behave appropriately within their roles and become more involved in their work (Brown &

Leigh, 1996: p.360). Therefore, when managers provide a work environment where employees can freely express themselves, they can increase employees' perceptions of psychological safety and foster a positive psychological climate.

According to Kahn (1990: p.692-724), when individuals perceive that the organization meets their psychological needs, they invest more time and energy in their work. This positively impacts individual motivation, task internalization and employee commitment. In this context, increased organizational contribution and a sense of validation positively influence the meaning an individual derives from their work and their perception of the psychological climate.

One factor that increases employee motivation is assigning employees to tasks that allow them to utilize their full skills and abilities and allow them to develop themselves. While job and task descriptions are crucial in determining the inherent difficulty of employees' jobs, managers can effectively match employees' skill levels with the opportunities available to utilize those skills (Bakker, 2005: p.27-28). This contributes to employee motivation and fosters a positive psychological climate.

According to Woerkom and Meyers (2015: p.83-84), the relationships employees develop with their managers influence their individual perceptions. This suggests that leader-member interaction has an impact on the perception of psychological climate. In this context, it can be argued that managers who develop quality relationships with employees, establish open and transparent communication are trustworthy, supportive and fair and grant autonomy can positively impact employees' perceptions of psychological climate. When psychological climate is combined with the supportive nature of managers, it creates a systemic integrity that increases employees' voluntary compliance, innovative participation and organizational citizenship behaviors. In this context, organizations should adopt holistic management approaches that are not solely based on technical skills but also consider psychological and ethical dimensions.

Our study has some limitations. The first is the applicability of generalizations based on the results of different studies to different organizations. Another limitation is the reliability of individual perceptions measured in these studies. Another limitation is the possibility that, due to the dynamic nature of the concept of psychological climate, studies may become inadequate in explaining the concept over time. Another limitation of the study is the adequacy of the existing literature in explaining the topic in all its dimensions.

Finally, perceptions of psychological climate can be influenced by many factors, including the physical characteristics of the workplace, job characteristics, personal characteristics, organizational culture, career opportunities, social activities, recognition, shared authority, a fair wage and reward system, collaboration and teamwork. Researchers can contribute to the literature by conducting new studies examining the impact of psychological climate on different variables and identifying new factors affecting psychological climate.

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